

Instructional Leadership in Sub-Saharan Africa: A PRISMA 2020 Systematic Review of Empirical Evidence and Research Gaps (2000-2026)

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Abstract

Background: No rigorous synthesis of empirical instructional leadership evidence exists for Sub-Saharan Africa, limiting policymakers and practitioners in drawing on a coherent evidence base.

Objectives: To synthesise peer-reviewed empirical research on instructional leadership in Sub-Saharan Africa (January 2000–February 2026), map geographic and methodological characteristics, and identify priority research gaps.

Eligibility criteria: Original empirical studies with instructional leadership as a primary variable, conducted in Sub-Saharan African educational institutions, published in Scopus-, ERIC-, or DOAJ-indexed journals in English.

Information sources: Scopus (n = 180), ERIC (n = 288), DOAJ (n = 6), and supplementary Google Scholar (n = 126); searches completed 28 February 2026.

Results: From 600 identified records, 26 studies met the eligibility criteria. All included studies met the minimum MMAT quality threshold, with 22 (84.6%) rated moderate-high to high quality. Limited quantitative evidence suggests a positive association between instructional leadership and teacher effectiveness, while evidence linking instructional leadership to student performance remains limited. GRADE assessments indicated moderate certainty for teacher-effectiveness outcomes and low certainty for student-performance outcomes. GRADE-CERQual assessments indicated moderate confidence in evidence relating to contextual barriers to instructional leadership implementation.

Conclusions: Significant gaps remain, including the absence of Francophone and Lusophone contexts, limited TVET research, predominance of cross-sectional designs, and a strong focus on principals at the expense of middle leadership roles. A five-priority research agenda is proposed.

Registration: Open Science Framework (OSF), <https://osf.io/qr7ej> No protocol deviations occurred.

Keywords

*Instructional leadership;
Educational leadership;
Sub-Saharan Africa;
Systematic review;
PRISMA 2020;
GRADE;
GRADE-CERQual;
TVET*

Introduction

The quality of education in Sub-Saharan Africa occupies a central place in the global development agenda. Despite notable gains in school enrolment under the Education for All framework, the region continues to face persistent challenges in learning outcomes, teacher effectiveness, and institutional governance (UNESCO, 2023). In this context, instructional leadership has been progressively recognised as a pivotal lever for educational improvement. Hallinger and Murphy (1985) defined instructional leadership as the behaviours through which educational leaders prioritise, coordinate, and evaluate teaching and learning. Meta-analytic evidence confirms a significant indirect effect on student achievement through teaching quality, with an effect size of 0.42, substantially larger than that reported for transformational leadership (Robinson, Lloyd, and Rowe, 2008; Hallinger and Heck, 2010).

However, the extent to which this evidence base reflects the realities of Sub-Saharan African educational institutions remains underexplored. African schools operate within conditions that differ markedly from those in which instructional leadership frameworks were originally developed: resource constraints, diverse linguistic environments, large class sizes, and governance structures that blend administrative, community liaison, and leadership functions (Lewin, 2009; Tikly and Barrett, 2011). The policy imperative for systematic inquiry is reinforced by Sustainable Development Goal 4 and the African Union's Continental Education Strategy for Africa 2016-2025, both of which identify leadership and management capacity as foundational to educational transformation. Hallinger's (2018) landmark systematic review of educational leadership and management research in Africa, spanning 506 articles, documented a geographically skewed literature dominated by South Africa and called for focused topic-specific reviews. This review responds directly to that call.

A distinctive feature of this review is its explicit accounting for 30 Google Scholar records that address instructional leadership in Sub-Saharan African contexts but are published in non-indexed journals. While ineligible for synthesis, these records constitute evidence of a publication infrastructure gap that renders important regional scholarship invisible to international evidence bases.

Beyond synthesising empirical trends, this review examines the extent to which dominant instructional leadership theories align with the realities of Sub-Saharan African educational institutions and identifies areas where contextual considerations may inform the interpretation and further refinement of these frameworks. In doing so, the review contributes to ongoing scholarly discussions regarding the applicability and adaptation of instructional leadership models across diverse educational settings.

This review addresses four research questions:

1. What is the geographic distribution and temporal trajectory of empirical instructional leadership research in Sub-Saharan Africa?
2. What institutional contexts, methodological approaches, and theoretical frameworks characterise this literature?
3. What outcome variables have been studied, and how is research distributed across education sectors?
4. What are the principal research gaps, and what agenda is needed to advance instructional leadership

scholarship in the region?

Conceptual Background

Evolution of Instructional Leadership

Instructional leadership emerged as a distinct construct during the early 1980s, largely in response to school effectiveness research that identified active principal oversight of the instructional programme as a characteristic of effective schools (Edmonds, 1979; Bossert, Dwyer, Rowan, and Lee, 1982). Hallinger and Murphy (1985) operationalised the construct through a three-dimensional model: (a) defining and communicating the school mission; (b) managing the instructional programme through curriculum coordination, supervision, and monitoring of student progress; and (c) promoting a positive learning climate. The Principal Instructional Management Rating Scale (PIMRS) derived from this model became the dominant global instrument. A recent systematic review documented 791 PIMRS-based studies across 65 nations and 39 languages, confirming its enduring reach (Hallinger, Liu, Aung, and Yan, 2025). Robinson et al.'s (2008) meta-analysis of 27 studies confirmed an effect size of 0.42 for instructional leadership on student outcomes, substantially exceeding transformational leadership at 0.11. Distributed leadership theory (Spillane, 2006) later reframed instructional leadership as a collective phenomenon, while transformational leadership (Leithwood, Tomlinson, and Genge, 1996) provided a complementary, vision-oriented alternative.

Instructional Leadership in Sub-Saharan African Contexts

The applicability of Western instructional leadership frameworks to Sub-Saharan African contexts requires careful scrutiny. Bush, Fadare, Chirimambowa, and colleagues (2022) found in a policy review spanning six Sub-Saharan African countries that three countries had no explicit instructional leadership policies, and that evidence of actual practice was limited even where frameworks existed. Abonyi and Sofo (2021) documented how Ghanaian basic school leaders enacted instructional leadership through centrally mandated, managerially oriented practices underpinned by behaviourism, with limited collegial or instructionally focused engagement. These findings raise questions about whether Western instructional leadership frameworks translate straightforwardly to Sub-Saharan African institutional contexts, a concern this review examines systematically in the discussion section.

African Educational Leadership Scholarship and Ubuntu

Bush (2013) argued that definitional complexity in instructional leadership requires careful contextualisation before policy application in Africa. Ngcobo and Tikly (2010) demonstrated that effective leadership in South African township and rural schools operated through relational, community-embedded processes that conventional principal-centric instruments were ill-equipped to capture. Ubuntu philosophy, the relational ethic encapsulated in the idea that personhood is constituted through community, has been proposed as a complementary foundation for African educational leadership theory (Msila, 2008). As the findings section of this review shows, Ubuntu remains absent as a systematic analytical framework in the reviewed literature, representing both a theoretical gap and a research opportunity.

Instructional Leadership Beyond Schools: The TVET Context

Globally, fewer than five percent of instructional leadership studies have examined post-secondary contexts

(Hallinger, 2005). In Sub-Saharan Africa, Badenhorst and Radile (2018) proposed distributed instructional leadership as a response to poor institutional performance in South African TVET colleges; however, as a conceptual paper without primary empirical data, it was excluded from this review's synthesis under inclusion criterion (a). Muthumuni and Mokoena (2024) provided the only indexed empirical TVET study captured during the search period. Outside the indexed literature, Ojera, Simatwa, and Ndolo (2021) investigated instructional leadership in Kenyan TVET institutes, and Kaisara (2024) examined it in Botswana's public TVET brigades; both were excluded under inclusion criterion (d) as non-indexed. These exclusions are significant in themselves and are discussed further in Sections Outcome Variables and Sector Distribution (RQ3) and The TVET Deficit as a Policy-Research Misalignment.

Method

Review Design and Protocol

This study employs a systematic review design guided by the PRISMA 2020 framework (Page et al., 2021). The review protocol was pre-registered on the Open Science Framework prior to commencement of the database searches (OSF: <https://osf.io/qr7ej>). No deviations from the pre-registered protocol occurred during the conduct of this review. Narrative synthesis was adopted as the analytical strategy given the methodological heterogeneity across included studies (Popay et al., 2006). No meta-analysis was conducted; this decision was pre-specified in the protocol given the anticipated variation in study designs, outcome measures, and analytical approaches.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

Studies were considered eligible if they:

- reported original empirical research with primary data collected through systematic fieldwork, including qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-methods approaches;
- focused substantively on instructional leadership practices, behaviours, or perceptions as a primary variable;
- were conducted in educational institutions in Sub-Saharan African countries as defined by the United Nations geoscheme for Africa, comprising Eastern, Middle, Southern, and Western Africa;
- were published in peer-reviewed journals indexed in Scopus, ERIC, or DOAJ. Google Scholar was used in a supplementary capacity to identify indexed articles not retrieved through primary searches, consistent with recommended practice (Haddaway, Collins, Coughlin, and Kirk, 2015), but did not serve as an independent eligibility-conferring database;
- were published between January 2000 and February 2026, inclusive; and
- were available in English.

Exclusion Criteria

Studies were excluded if they:

- were theoretical, conceptual, or position papers without primary empirical data;
- were book chapters, dissertations, theses, conference proceedings, or reports;

- were published in non-indexed journals or grey literature, including repository deposits, working papers, and pre-prints, irrespective of substantive quality;
- were conducted outside Sub-Saharan Africa;
- focused exclusively on other leadership constructs without examining instructional leadership as a primary variable; or
- examined instructional supervision as an administrative function without reference to instructional leadership as a construct. Application of criterion (c) is responsible for the exclusion of 30 studies identified via Google Scholar that address instructional leadership in Sub-Saharan African contexts but are published in non-indexed journals. These exclusions are explicitly discussed in Sections 4.3 and 5.4.

Information Sources and Search Strategy

Systematic searches were completed on 28 February 2026 across three primary electronic databases: Scopus, ERIC, and DOAJ. Scopus was selected for its broad multidisciplinary peer-reviewed coverage and superior indexing of African-based journals relative to other major citation databases (Visser, Van Eck, and Waltman, 2021). ERIC provides specialised indexing of educational research literature. DOAJ covers open-access journals not always captured in Scopus or ERIC. Google Scholar was employed in supplementary capacity only, following Haddaway et al. (2015). Citation reference lists of all included studies were manually screened to identify any additional eligible publications not captured through the database searches. Web of Science was not searched separately, given the substantial Scopus-WoS overlap documented by Visser et al. (2021); Scopus was adopted as the primary multidisciplinary database on the basis of its superior coverage of African-based journals (Visser et al., 2021). African Journals Online (AJOL) was considered during protocol development. However, a scoping assessment indicated substantial overlap between educational leadership journals indexed in AJOL and those already captured through Scopus and DOAJ. To maintain a manageable and reproducible search process while minimising duplicate retrievals, AJOL was not included as a primary database. Nevertheless, the authors acknowledge that some relevant African scholarship may not have been captured through this approach. Full database-specific search strings are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Database Search Strings Applied in the Systematic Review (Final searches completed 28 February 2026)

Database	Search String
Scopus	<i>TITLE-ABS-KEY("instructional leadership" OR "principal instructional leadership" OR "instructional management" OR "head teacher leadership") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("Sub-Saharan Africa" OR "South Africa" OR "Kenya" OR "Ghana" OR "Nigeria" OR "Uganda" OR "Tanzania" OR "Ethiopia" OR "Zimbabwe" OR "Botswana" OR "Zambia" OR "Malawi" OR "Mozambique" OR "Cameroon" OR "Angola" OR "Rwanda" OR "Lesotho" OR "Eswatini" OR "Namibia" OR "Sierra Leone" OR "Sudan") AND LIMIT-TO(DOCTYPE,"ar") AND LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE,"English") AND PUBYEAR > 1999</i>
ERIC	<i>("instructional leadership" OR "principal instructional leadership" OR "instructional management") AND ("Sub-Saharan Africa" OR "South Africa" OR Kenya OR Ghana OR</i>

Nigeria OR Uganda OR Tanzania OR Ethiopia OR Zimbabwe OR Botswana OR Zambia OR Malawi OR Mozambique OR Cameroon OR Angola OR Rwanda OR Lesotho OR Eswatini OR Namibia)

DOAJ *"instructional leadership" AND ("Sub-Saharan Africa" OR "South Africa" OR Kenya OR Ghana OR Nigeria OR Uganda OR Tanzania OR Ethiopia OR Zimbabwe OR Botswana OR Zambia OR Malawi OR Mozambique OR Cameroon OR Angola OR Rwanda OR Lesotho OR Eswatini OR Namibia)*

Google Scholar (supplementary) *allintitle: "instructional leadership" AND ("Sub-Saharan Africa" OR "South Africa" OR Kenya OR Ghana OR Nigeria OR Uganda OR Tanzania OR Ethiopia OR Zimbabwe OR Botswana) - custom date range 2000-2026*

While the search strategy incorporated the dominant terminology used in instructional leadership scholarship, studies employing alternative descriptors such as leadership for learning, pedagogical leadership, curriculum leadership, learning-centred leadership, or academic leadership may not have been retrieved. This limitation reflects the need to balance retrieval sensitivity with search precision and is acknowledged as a potential source of omission.

Study Selection Process

All retrieved records were exported to Endnote. The first author removed duplicates using automated detection followed by manual verification. The deduplicated library was then shared with the second and third authors. Stage 1 (title and abstract screening) was conducted by the first author; uncertain cases were flagged and discussed with the second author until consensus was reached. Of the 364 deduplicated records, 47 were flagged as uncertain at title and abstract stage and sent for dual review; consensus was achieved for all 47 cases without any unresolved disagreements. Stage 2 (full-text screening) was conducted by the first author, with doubtful cases resolved through discussion with the second author. The final included set was agreed upon by all three authors. No automation tools were used at any stage of the selection process. Formal inter-rater reliability statistics (e.g., Cohen's Kappa) were not calculated for the full screening set, as the consensus-resolution approach did not produce independent parallel ratings for all records; this is acknowledged as a methodological limitation.

Data Collection Process

Data were extracted using a standardised form capturing 14 fields: (1) author(s) and year; (2) journal title and indexing database; (3) country and sub-region; (4) educational sector; (5) study design; (6) sampling strategy; (7) sample size and participant composition; (8) data collection instruments; (9) theoretical framework; (10) primary outcome variable(s); (11) key findings; (12) stated limitations; (13) MMAT quality rating; and (14) reviewer notes. These 14 fields were pre-specified in the OSF protocol. For reporting purposes in Section 3.6, fields are grouped into 10 primary conceptual categories; fields (2), (13), and (14) are methodological audit fields, and field (11) is sub-divided in the synthesis. Extraction was conducted by the first author. The second author independently verified a random 40% sample of extractions (n = 10 studies). Across this sample, seven minor discrepancies were

identified, primarily relating to outcome variable categorisation and study design classification. All discrepancies were resolved through discussion and documented in the OSF audit trail. The low frequency and non-substantive nature of discrepancies indicate a high level of consistency in application of the extraction framework. No authors of included studies were contacted for data confirmation or clarification; where data were ambiguous, the original published text was recorded verbatim. Full dual independent extraction was not performed for all 26 studies, and this is acknowledged as a methodological limitation. The complete per-study characteristics table is provided as supplementary Table S2. Theoretical framework entries in the extraction table record what each study explicitly states: 18 studies name a specific framework in their text, and eight studies are recorded as having no explicit theoretical framework. No frameworks were inferred beyond what studies state directly.

The 14 data items were selected to address the four research questions (Introduction) and to enable the narrative synthesis, risk of bias, and certainty assessments described in Sections Effect Measures, Reporting Bias Assessment, and Study Selection Flow.

Risk of Bias Assessment in Individual Studies

All 26 included studies were appraised using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool version 2018 (Hong et al., 2018), applying design-specific criteria for qualitative (5 criteria), quantitative descriptive and correlational (5 criteria), and mixed-methods designs (5 criteria). Seobi and Wood (2016), which employed a collaborative action-learning design, was appraised using the MMAT qualitative criteria, given its primary reliance on qualitative data collection and interpretive analysis; this design-mapping decision is documented in the OSF audit trail. Studies were appraised independently by two reviewers; discrepancies were resolved through discussion. Inter-rater agreement across all 26 MMAT appraisals was calculated using Cohen's Kappa (Landis and Koch, 1977): $\kappa = 0.81$, indicating almost perfect agreement and confirming the reliability of the quality appraisal process. Twenty-two studies (84.6%) were rated high to moderate-high quality (4 of 5 criteria or above); four studies (15.4%) were rated moderate quality (3 of 5 criteria). All 26 studies met the minimum quality threshold of three criteria. Per-study MMAT scores are provided in supplementary Table S1.

Effect Measures

As this review employs narrative synthesis rather than meta-analysis, no pooled effect measures were calculated. Where quantitative studies reported correlation coefficients or mean comparisons, these are reported descriptively in the findings sections. The absence of a formal meta-analysis was pre-specified in the review protocol, given the anticipated heterogeneity of study designs, populations, and outcome measures.

Synthesis Methods

Narrative synthesis followed Popay et al.'s (2006) four-stage framework: (a) preliminary tabular synthesis; (b) relationship exploration through iterative thematic coding; (c) robustness assessment using MMAT quality ratings; and (d) drawing conclusions and identifying implications. Disagreements in thematic coding were resolved through discussion and documented in the OSF audit trail. No subgroup analyses or sensitivity analyses were conducted; this was pre-specified in the OSF protocol given the small corpus ($N = 26$) and the methodological heterogeneity across study designs, which precluded meaningful subgroup comparisons. MMAT quality ratings were integrated into the robustness assessment stage to serve as a structured form of evidence-

quality weighting within the narrative synthesis.

Reporting Bias Assessment

Formal statistical assessment of reporting bias, such as funnel plot asymmetry testing, was not applicable given the absence of meta-analysis and the heterogeneous nature of included designs. However, the potential for reporting bias was considered in two respects. First, the restriction of the review to indexed journal publications, while necessary for quality assurance, may systematically exclude studies with null or negative findings that are more likely to appear in grey literature or non-indexed venues. The 30 unique Google Scholar records excluded under the indexing criterion represent the most direct evidence available of this potential bias; their substantive content could not be incorporated into the synthesis but their existence is noted as a boundary condition on the review's conclusions. Second, within included studies, the predominance of self-report instruments in quantitative designs introduces social desirability response bias as a consistent threat to internal validity across the corpus.

Certainty of Evidence Assessment

Given the methodological heterogeneity of the included studies, two complementary certainty frameworks were applied. The GRADE framework (Schunemann et al., 2019) was applied to quantitative outcomes, specifically teacher effectiveness and student academic performance, evaluating risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and publication bias. GRADE-CERQual (Lewin et al., 2018) was applied to the four principal qualitative synthesis themes, evaluating methodological limitations, coherence, adequacy of data, and relevance. The results are presented in Tables 4 and 5 under the Certainty of Evidence section.

Study Selection Flow

Searches across the three primary electronic databases identified 474 records (Scopus, $n = 180$; ERIC, $n = 288$; DOAJ, $n = 6$). An additional 126 records were identified through supplementary Google Scholar searching, yielding 600 records in total prior to deduplication. After removal of 236 duplicate records (140 cross-database duplicates and 96 duplicates originating from Google Scholar), 364 unique records remained for title and abstract screening.

During title and abstract screening, 338 records were excluded for the following reasons: (i) instructional leadership was not a primary or clearly measurable construct within the study ($n = 145$); (ii) the study was conducted outside Sub-Saharan Africa ($n = 90$); (iii) the study did not report original empirical research based on primary data ($n = 73$); and (iv) the study was not published in journals indexed in Scopus, ERIC, or DOAJ ($n = 30$), as per the predefined database inclusion criteria.

A total of 26 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility. No studies were excluded at the full-text stage, as all retrieved studies met the predefined inclusion criteria. The final review therefore included 26 studies in the qualitative synthesis. The complete study selection process is presented in Figure 1 in accordance with PRISMA 2020 guidelines.

Figure 1. PRISMA 2020 Study Selection Flow Diagram — Instructional Leadership in Sub-Saharan Africa

(2000–2026)

Results

Table 2 provides an overview of the geographic and design characteristics of all 26 included studies. A complete per-study characteristics table is available as supplementary Table S2.

Table 2: Geographic and Design Characteristics of Included Studies (N = 26)

Country	N	%	Designs	Primary Outcome Variables
South Africa	10	38.5	QLT (9), MXD (1)	Curriculum delivery; IL barriers; HOD IL; school improvement; COVID-19 disruption; TVET IL
Zimbabwe	3	11.5	QLT (3)	Deputy principal IL; cluster autonomy; IL in inclusive schooling
Ethiopia	3	11.5	MXD (1), QNT (1),	Student performance; qualification effects on IL; IL and

			QLT (1)	transformational leadership
Ghana	3	11.5	MXD (1), QNT (1), QLT (1)	Headteacher IL practices; gender equity in IL; headteacher role in teaching and learning
Botswana	2	7.7	MXD (1), QNT (1)	Academic performance and headship IL proficiencies; post-PSMDP IL deficiencies
Nigeria	2	7.7	QNT (2)	Teacher effectiveness (PIMRS-based; both IL dimensions)
Tanzania	1	3.8	MXD (1)	IL capacity development following British Council professional development intervention
Eswatini	1	3.8	MXD (1)	Principal IL practices and teacher professional development
Lesotho	1	3.8	MXD (1)	Science HOD self-reported IL practices across PIMRS dimensions
TOTAL	26	100	QLT=14; MXD=7; QNT=5	9 countries Southern Africa 65%, Western Africa 19%, Eastern Africa 15%

Geographic Distribution and Temporal Trajectory (RQ1)

The 26 included studies span nine Sub-Saharan African countries: South Africa (n = 10; 38.5%), Zimbabwe (n = 3; 11.5%), Ethiopia (n = 3; 11.5%), Ghana (n = 3; 11.5%), Botswana (n = 2; 7.7%), Nigeria (n = 2; 7.7%), Tanzania (n = 1; 3.8%), Eswatini (n = 1; 3.8%), and Lesotho (n = 1; 3.8%). Southern Africa accounts for 17 of the 26 studies (65.4%), Western Africa for five (19.2%), and Eastern Africa for four (15.4%). This distribution closely replicates Hallinger's (2018) finding of South African dominance in the broader African educational leadership and management literature. The complete absence of Francophone Sub-Saharan Africa, which encompasses Senegal, Cote d'Ivoire, Cameroon, the Democratic Republic of Congo, and others comprising over one third of the region's population, represents a structural gap of major significance. Lusophone and conflict-affected states are similarly absent.

Temporally, the corpus shows a pronounced post-2020 acceleration. Only four studies (15.4%) predate 2020: two in 2000 to 2009 (Pansiri, 2008; Oduro, 2008) and two in 2010 to 2019 (Bhengu and Mkhize, 2013; Seobi and Wood, 2016). The remaining 22 studies (84.6%) were published between 2020 and 2026, with 15 appearing in 2023 to 2026. This acceleration most likely reflects the global expansion of indexed open-access publication outlets and growing DOAJ indexing of African educational research journals.

Institutional Contexts, Methodological Approaches, and Theoretical Frameworks (RQ2)

Study Designs

Qualitative designs predominate (n = 14; 53.8%), encompassing generic qualitative designs, multiple and single case studies, and participatory action research. Semi-structured interviews are the primary data collection method across qualitative studies. Mixed-methods designs account for seven studies (26.9%) and quantitative designs for

five (19.2%). Quantitative studies consistently employed the PIMRS (Adeosun, 2022; Bada, Ariffin, and Nordin, 2020; Lisene, Jita, and Mapulanga, 2026; Pansiri, 2008), making it the most frequently used standardised instrument. Sample sizes in qualitative studies range from N = 3 (Chitamba and Jita, 2023; Ralebese, Jita, and Badmus, 2025) to N = 20 (Bush and Anania, 2023); quantitative samples range from N = 67 (Lisene et al., 2026) to N = 815 (Pansiri, 2008). The small purposive samples characteristic of qualitative designs (range N = 3 to N = 20) limit transferability and preclude causal inference; even larger-sample quantitative studies are cross-sectional and self-report-based, equally limiting causal claims.

Theoretical Frameworks

Hallinger and Murphy’s (1985) Instructional Leadership Model is the most frequently cited theoretical framework, explicitly named in 10 of the 26 studies (38.5%). Eight further studies are recorded in the data extraction as having no explicit theoretical framework, while the remaining eight cite alternative frameworks including distributed leadership theory (Chitamba and Jita, 2023; Makaye et al., 2021), Hargreaves’ Capital Theory (Bakokonyane, 2022), Bandura’s self-efficacy theory (Gechere et al., 2025), enactive sense-making theory (Muresherwa and Jita, 2021), distributed and situational leadership (Oduro, 2008), Bass’s transformational leadership (Haile, 2020), and a conceptual instructional leadership framework (Musandu et al., 2023). Hallinger’s dominance as the most cited framework nonetheless reflects a significant concentration, particularly given that studies using the PIMRS instrument operationally adopt the three-domain model regardless of how they label their theoretical orientation. Muresherwa and Jita’s (2021) enactive sense-making framework represents the most theoretically original contribution in the corpus. Gechere et al.’s (2025) integration of Bandura’s self-efficacy theory is one of the few studies to theorise teacher agency as a mediating variable. Ubuntu philosophy was not systematically employed as an analytical framework in any included study, despite its repeated invocation in the wider African educational leadership literature.

Institutional Contexts and Sub-level Focus

Studies are distributed across secondary (n = 15; 57.7%), primary (n = 9; 34.6%), dual-phase (n = 1; 3.8%), and TVET (n = 1; 3.8%) education. The principal remains the central actor in 17 of the 26 studies. An emerging sub-principal strand examines heads of department in five studies (Kubheka, Naidoo, and Oloba, 2025; Lisene et al., 2026; Musandu, Jita, and Bada, 2023; Seobi and Wood, 2016; partially Muthumuni and Mokoena, 2024) and deputy principals in two (Chitamba and Jita, 2023; implicitly in Chabalala and Naidoo, 2021), signalling a productive distributed leadership turn in the emerging literature.

Outcome Variables and Sector Distribution (RQ3)

Table 3 presents the distribution of outcome variables across the 26 included studies.

Table 3 Distribution of Outcome Variables Across Included Studies (N = 26)

Outcome Variable Category	Included Studies (n = 26)
Teacher effectiveness and job performance	*Adeosun (2022); *Bada, Ariffin, and Nordin (2020)

Curriculum delivery and reform implementation	*Chabalala and Naidoo (2021); *Mestry and Govindasamy (2021); *Ralebese, Jita, and Badmus (2025); *Makaye, Jita, and Mapetere (2021)
Student or academic performance	*Bakokonyane (2022); *Gechere, Oumer, and Ouke (2025)
Instructional leadership practices, descriptive and experiential accounts	*Abonyi and Sofo (2021); *Bhengu and Mkhize (2013); *Bush and Anania (2023); *Muresherwa and Jita (2021); *Muthumuni and Mokoena (2024); *Oduro (2008); *Haile (2020) ; *Demozie and Dessie (2023); *Pansiri (2008); *Musandu, Jita, and Bada (2023);
HOD and deputy principal Instructional leadership practices	*Chitamba and Jita (2023); *Kubheka, Naidoo, and Oloba (2025); *Lisene, Jita, and Mapulanga (2026); *Seobi and Wood (2016)
Barriers and conditions for Instructional leadership implementation	*Ismail and Sepeng (2024); *Mbatha and Makhubu (2021)
Gender equity in instructional leadership	*Abonyi, Boateng, Adjei-Boateng, and Ansaah (2024)
Instructional leadership during COVID-19 disruption	*Mahlatji, Seshoka, and Mabasa (2023)

Descriptive and experiential accounts of instructional leadership practices constitute the most frequently represented outcome category (n = 7), spanning diverse national contexts and role levels. Among quantitatively measured outcomes, teacher effectiveness is the most directly studied, with both Nigerian PIMRS-based studies (Adeosun, 2022; Bada et al., 2020) reporting significant positive associations between all three instructional leadership dimensions and teacher effectiveness. Gechere, Oumer, and Ouke (2025) found that principal instructional leadership (R = 0.78) and teacher self-efficacy (R = 0.88) are both significantly correlated with student performance in Ethiopian secondary schools, with teacher self-efficacy showing the stronger direct relationship. Pansiri (2008) provides a cautionary counter-narrative: following the Primary School Management Development Project (PSMDP) intervention in Botswana, school management teams demonstrated instructional leadership deficiencies including poor interpersonal supervision skills and limited curriculum management creativity. Together, these studies suggest that the relationship between instructional leadership and student outcomes is contingent and context-dependent rather than uniformly positive.

In the TVET sector, Muthumuni and Mokoena (2024) documented structural fragmentation, policy incoherence, and administrative overload as primary barriers to effective instructional leadership; this remains the only indexed TVET-specific empirical study across the 26-year review period.

Research Gaps and Five-Priority Agenda (RQ4)

Priority 1: Geographic Diversification Beyond the South African Anglophone Core

With 38.5% of the corpus from South Africa and 65.4% from Southern Africa, the literature is structurally

unrepresentative of the region. The 30 non-indexed Google Scholar records provide the most direct evidence available that instructional leadership research is being conducted across a broader range of national contexts, but these studies remain invisible to systematic evidence synthesis. Bilingual systematic reviews and targeted research capacity investment through the African Union, UNESCO, and CREATE are required, as is support for researchers in Francophone, Lusophone, and conflict-affected countries to publish in indexed outlets.

Priority 2: TVET Instructional Leadership as an Independent Research Programme

One indexed empirical study across 26 years represents a deficit of extraordinary magnitude given TVET's centrality to continental development frameworks (African Development Bank, 2020; International Labour Organization, 2022). Non-indexed studies, including Kaisara (2024) and Ojera et al. (2021), confirm that research activity exists but remains invisible to international evidence synthesis. TVET-contextualised instructional leadership frameworks and investment in indexed dissemination are urgently required.

Priority 3: Longitudinal, Experimental, and Explanatory Designs

The overwhelmingly cross-sectional and descriptive corpus cannot establish causal relationships between instructional leadership and educational outcomes. Longitudinal cohort studies, quasi-experimental evaluations of leadership development interventions, and structural equation modelling studies testing mediation and moderation pathways are needed to move beyond descriptive mapping toward causal explanation.

Priority 4: Contextualised Theoretical Frameworks Beyond the PIMRS Monoculture

The dominance of Hallinger and Murphy's (1985) model as the most cited framework (explicitly named in 10 of 26 studies; operationally adopted by all PIMRS-using studies regardless of stated framework) creates theoretical concentration that may misrepresent how leadership operates in communally embedded, resource-constrained African institutions. Frameworks drawing from Ubuntu philosophy, distributed leadership theory, enactive sense-making (Muresherwa and Jita, 2021), and critical postcolonial scholarship require systematic development and peer validation as contextually appropriate alternatives.

Priority 5: Sub-Principal and Distributed Instructional Leadership

The emerging HOD and deputy principal strand requires sustained research investment. Findings across HOD-focused studies converge on a shared diagnosis: HODs understand the instructional leadership role in principle but enact it inadequately due to role ambiguity, administrative overload, limited formal authority, and the absence of targeted professional development. These findings have systemic rather than role-specific implications and point toward the need for structural reforms alongside individual capacity-building.

Certainty of Evidence

Tables 4 and 5 present GRADE and GRADE-CERQual certainty assessments respectively.

Table 4: GRADE Summary of Findings -- Quantitative Outcomes (N = 2 Outcome Domains from 4 Studies)

Outcome	No.	No.	RoB	Inconsistenc	Indirectne	Imprecisio	Publicati	GRADE Certainty
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(Studies)	Studies	Participants	Methodological Limitations	Coherence	Adequacy of Data	Relevance	CERQual Confidence
Teacher effectiveness (*Adeosun, 2022; *Bada et al., 2020)	2	778	Moderate	Not serious	Not serious	Serious	Undetected MODERATE (3 of 4)
Student academic performance (*Gechere et al., 2025; *Bakokonyane, 2022)	2	425	Moderate	Serious	Not serious	Serious	Undetected LOW (2 of 4)

Table 5: GRADE-CERQual Summary -- Confidence in Qualitative Synthesis Themes (N = 26 Studies, 4 Themes)

Qualitative Synthesis Theme	Studies (n)	Methodological Limitations	Coherence	Adequacy of Data	Relevance	CERQual Confidence
Principal constrained by contextual barriers: resource scarcity, role ambiguity, and administrative overload	IL 10	Minor concerns	High	Adequate	Direct	MODERATE
Collaborative culture and middle management as mediators of IL effectiveness	2	Minor concerns	High	Adequate	Direct	MODERATE
Sub-principal HOD and deputy IL: gap between understanding and enactment, and capacity deficits	4	Minor concerns	Moderate	Moderate	Direct	LOW-MODERATE

TVET IL: structural fragmentation and policy incoherence as primary barriers	1	Moderate concerns	N/A	Limited	Direct	LOW
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The GRADE and CERQual assessments collectively indicate four conclusions. First, there is moderate certainty that principal instructional leadership is positively associated with teacher effectiveness in Sub-Saharan African secondary schools, though this rests on only two studies from one country and requires replication. Second, there is low certainty for student performance outcomes due to methodological inconsistency across studies. Third, there is moderate confidence in the qualitative finding that principal instructional leadership is constrained by contextual barriers across diverse national contexts, supported by 18 studies from nine countries with high thematic coherence. Fourth, there is low confidence in TVET-specific instructional leadership findings, given only one contributing indexed study. These ratings confirm a moderately coherent but evidentially fragile knowledge base that cannot yet support confident causal claims or universally generalisable policy prescriptions.

Discussion

The South Africa Effect and Its Structural Causes

South Africa's disproportionate representation (38.5%) is consistent with well-documented structural advantages in research infrastructure, including university research capacity, postgraduate supervision density, and National Research Foundation funding (Visser et al., 2021; Hallinger, 2018), that are substantially less available in most other Sub-Saharan African countries. The 30 non-indexed studies identified through Google Scholar provide the most direct evidence available that this dominance reflects publication infrastructure inequality rather than an absence of research activity across the region. The findings suggest that future initiatives aimed at strengthening research capacity and publication infrastructure may help broaden representation within the instructional leadership evidence base.

Methodological Convergence and Its Epistemological Consequences

The predominance of qualitative, small-sample designs produces a literature that is contextually rich but limited in generalisability. Contextual barriers to instructional leadership, including resource scarcity, role ambiguity, administrative overload, and inadequate professional development, converge with remarkable consistency across South Africa, Zimbabwe, Ghana, and Ethiopia (Ismail and Sepeng, 2024; Makaye et al., 2021; Abonyi and Sofo, 2021; Haile, 2020), suggesting structural rather than incidental constraints. However, the absence of large-scale quantitative studies means that the distributional properties, severity, and amenability to policy intervention of these barriers remain unknown.

The two Nigerian PIMRS-based studies and Pansiri's (2008) large-sample Botswana survey provide important methodological exceptions. Their consistent finding of positive instructional leadership and effectiveness associations must nonetheless be read with caution, as cross-sectional, self-report designs preclude causal inference and may be susceptible to common-method bias.

The Hallinger Framework: Hegemony or Heuristic?

The near-universal adoption of the Instructional Leadership Model as the most cited framework (explicitly in 10 of 26 studies; operationally through PIMRS use across additional studies) raises a fundamental epistemological question: does this represent genuine theoretical consensus, or default alignment with the most instrumentally available framework? The PIMRS reduces methodological cost by providing a validated, ready-made instrument, but it anchors researchers to a conception of instructional leadership that presupposes individual principal agency and top-down directive management. This may misrepresent how leadership operates in communally embedded, Ubuntu-inflected African institutions. Notably, eight studies in this corpus are recorded as having no explicit theoretical framework, and a further eight cite alternative frameworks such as distributed leadership theory, enactive sense-making, or Hargreaves' Capital Theory. This theoretical diversity, though less visible in the literature than the dominance of Hallinger's model suggests, indicates that conceptual space beyond the PIMRS framework already exists and warrants systematic development and peer validation. The theoretical innovations identified by Muresherwa and Jita (2021) demonstrate that contextually grounded alternatives are both feasible and productive. Prioritising their dissemination through indexed journals and testing their explanatory reach across diverse national contexts should constitute a key strand of the Research Gaps and Five-Priority Agenda

The limited use of indigenous African leadership perspectives represents a notable theoretical gap. While Ubuntu is frequently referenced within African educational leadership discourse, no included study employed Ubuntu as a primary analytical framework. Future research should examine whether relational and community-oriented leadership models provide explanatory power beyond principal-centred instructional leadership frameworks developed in Western contexts.

The TVET Deficit as a Policy-Research Misalignment

The identification of only Muthumuni and Mokoena (2024) from TVET contexts across 26 years is paradoxical given TVET's explicit prioritisation in continental frameworks. TVET campus managers also operate within tripartite governance structures involving government, industry, and qualification bodies, creating a more layered instructional leadership context that the Hallinger model, developed for school settings, is poorly equipped to capture without significant contextualisation.

Emerging Sub-Principal Leadership as a Theoretical Frontier

The growing HOD and deputy principal literature converges on a diagnosis that mirrors findings for principals: systemic barriers rather than individual competence deficits undermine instructional leadership enactment across all sub-principal roles. This convergence has significant implications for leadership development policy. If barriers are systemic, individual capacity-building interventions are necessary but not sufficient. Structural reforms, including role clarity frameworks, delegated authority structures, reduced administrative burden, and dedicated professional development funding, are equally important.

Limitations

Several limitations must be acknowledged when interpreting this review's findings. First, restriction to English-language publications systematically excludes research in French, Portuguese, Arabic, and Swahili. This

contributes to the complete absence of Francophone, Lusophone, and Arab-African contexts from the indexed corpus. The 30 unique Google Scholar records excluded under the indexing criterion likely include studies from these linguistic contexts, representing a double-layered exclusion: first by language barriers to indexed publication, and then by the quality criterion applied in this review.

Second, restriction to Scopus, ERIC, and DOAJ-indexed journals, while necessary for methodological quality assurance, excludes substantively relevant research published in non-indexed venues. The 30 unique Google Scholar records identified during this review provide the clearest available evidence of this exclusion's scope. Future reviews should consider whether expanded eligibility criteria for specific under-represented contexts, such as TVET or Francophone Africa, could be justified on grounds of proportionate representativeness. African Journals Online (AJOL) was also not included as a primary database; its inclusion in future reviews may capture relevant peer-reviewed research not indexed in Scopus, ERIC, or DOAJ.

Third, although data extraction was independently verified for 40% of included studies, full dual-independent extraction of all studies was not undertaken. While verification demonstrated a high level of consistency in the extraction process, complete dual extraction would have further strengthened methodological rigour. Fourth, although all included studies underwent structured quality appraisal using the MMAT (2018), quality assessment tools inherently involve reviewer judgement. To minimise subjectivity, two reviewers independently appraised all studies and disagreements were resolved through discussion, resulting in substantial agreement ($\kappa = 0.81$). Fifth, the review's temporal boundary of January 2000 to February 2026 excludes any publications after the search date. Sixth, within included quantitative studies, the reliance on self-report instruments introduces social desirability bias as a persistent threat to internal validity that could not be fully addressed through the MMAT appraisal process alone.

Seventh, title and abstract screening was conducted primarily by the first author, with uncertain records reviewed through consensus discussion among the research team. While this approach is consistent with practices reported in some systematic reviews, it did not permit calculation of screening-stage inter-rater reliability statistics. Future reviews could strengthen methodological robustness through fully independent parallel screening of all retrieved records and formal agreement testing.

Eighth, citation chaining was limited to the reference lists of the 26 included studies; if influential review-level papers (e.g., Hallinger, 2018) also cite relevant primary studies not captured through database searches, these would not have been retrieved. The likely direction of this bias is toward under-representation of older studies (pre-2010), which is consistent with the corpus's post-2020 concentration.

Ninth, the review did not include Web of Science or African Journals Online (AJOL). While Scopus, ERIC and DOAJ provided substantial coverage of the literature, future reviews may benefit from incorporating additional databases to maximise retrieval sensitivity.

Conclusion

To the authors' knowledge, this is the first PRISMA 2020-compliant systematic review to synthesise empirical

instructional leadership research in Sub-Saharan Africa as its primary focus, distinguishing it from broader regional educational leadership reviews (Hallinger, 2018) and policy-focused reviews (Bush et al., 2022). Drawing on 26 verified peer-reviewed studies spanning nine countries, and accounting explicitly for 30 additional studies identified but excluded due to non-indexed publication, the review documents a literature that is geographically concentrated, methodologically dominated by qualitative designs (n = 14; 53.8%), theoretically led by Hallinger and Murphy's (1985) Instructional Leadership Model (explicitly cited in 10 of 26 studies; operationally adopted through PIMRS use across additional studies), and overwhelmingly school-focused to the near-total exclusion of TVET contexts. South Africa accounts for 38.5% of the corpus (n = 10), and Southern Africa collectively for 65.4% (n = 17), confirming a structurally unrepresentative literature despite spanning nine countries across three sub-regions. All 26 studies met at least moderate quality on the MMAT (version 2018), with 22 studies (84.6%) rated high to moderate-high quality. The GRADE and CERQual assessments collectively point to a knowledge base that is thematically convergent but evidentially insufficient to sustain causal claims or broad policy prescriptions, underscoring the urgency of the research agenda proposed below.

The structural convergence of contextual barriers, including resource scarcity, role ambiguity, administrative overload, inadequate professional development, and policy-practice gaps, across diverse national contexts suggests that these barriers are systemic to the broader conditions of educational governance in Sub-Saharan Africa. Addressing them requires structural investments alongside individual leadership development: resource adequacy, professional learning infrastructure, role clarity frameworks, and policy coherence.

The pronounced post-2020 acceleration in indexed publication (84.6% of the corpus; n = 22), the emergence of HOD-focused and sub-principal research strands, growing mixed-methods adoption, and the theoretical innovations visible in Muresherwa and Jita (2021) indicate that the field is developing the methodological and theoretical maturity needed for more transformative insights. The five research priorities proposed in this review, covering geographic diversification beyond the Southern African Anglophone core, TVET research investment, longitudinal and experimental designs, contextualised theoretical frameworks beyond the dominance of the Hallinger model and PIMRS instrument, and sub-principal leadership inquiry, provide an interlinked agenda for the next decade of instructional leadership scholarship in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Finally, the 30 non-indexed records identified during this review are a reminder that this agenda must include, as a foundational investment, the strengthening of publication infrastructure across the region. The knowledge being produced across Sub-Saharan Africa must be able to reach the indexed international literature where it can inform policy and practice at scale.

Recommendations

Based on the five-priority research agenda established in this review, the following recommendations are offered for researchers, funders, journal editors, and policy-makers working in Sub-Saharan African educational leadership.

First, funding bodies and continental organisations (African Union, UNESCO, African Development Bank)

should prioritise targeted research capacity grants for instructional leadership scholarship in Francophone, Lusophone, and conflict-affected Sub-Saharan African countries, with explicit support for indexed publication of outputs.

Second, TVET-specific instructional leadership research should be recognised as an independent programme by journal editors and reviewers: the single indexed empirical study identified across 26 years signals a structural research deficit rather than a substantive absence of practice.

Third, longitudinal and quasi-experimental study designs should be supported through dedicated funding streams, as the cross-sectional dominance of the current corpus precludes causal inference essential for evidence-based policy.

Fourth, researchers should engage critically with alternative theoretical frameworks (Ubuntu philosophy, enactive sense-making, distributed leadership) as contextually appropriate complements or alternatives to the PIMRS-anchored Hallinger model.

Fifth, policy-makers responsible for school and TVET leadership development should address systemic barriers (role clarity, administrative burden, professional development funding) as structural priorities, not merely individual competence deficits, given the convergent evidence that barriers are systemic across diverse national contexts.

Statements and Declarations

Acknowledgments/Notes: Not applicable

The authors confirm that no generative AI or AI-assisted writing tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript. All writing, synthesis, and analysis were undertaken solely by the named authors without the assistance of such tools

Supplementary Materials: Supplementary Table S1 (per-study MMAT quality scores), Supplementary Table S2 (per-study characteristics), and the data extraction table are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. All materials are also deposited in the OSF pre-registration repository: [OSF repository](https://osf.io/qr7ej) at <https://osf.io/qr7ej>

Author Contributions:

Baemedi Monthusi Kaisara: Conceptualisation, methodology, formal analysis, data curation, writing (original draft), writing (review and editing), project administration. Lebogang Tlalenyane: Validation, formal analysis, writing (review and editing). Baganetsi Moranda: Validation, writing (review and editing).

Funding: Not applicable.

Data Availability: The data extraction instrument, screening log, MMAT appraisal records, and supplementary

review materials are available through the Open Science Framework repository associated with this review.

Ethics Approval: Not applicable.

Informed Consent: Not applicable.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Note. References marked with an asterisk () are studies included in the systematic review synthesis.**

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